

Session E

**CHEMISTRY AND
CHEMICAL
COMPOUNDS IN
BIOLOGY,
AGRICULTURE AND
MEDICINE**

**OBTAINING ACTIVE DRY WINE YEAST
BIOMASS AT THE MICROPILOT LEVEL**

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A *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strain, isolated from “Fetească regală” grapes cultivated in “Pietroasa” Viticulture and Winemaking Research and Development Center, belonging to the University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest (USAMV) and identified by molecular sequencing, was used for cultivation on a synthetic medium to obtain active dry yeast biomass. The scale-up from laboratory level at micropilot level was performed in this study, following the optimization of the process at laboratory level. The pre-inoculum was based on pure culture of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* which was used to inoculate a liquid YSP medium (yeast extract, hy-soy peptone, and sucrose) to obtain the liquid inoculum. The liquid inoculum was used to inoculate the fermentation medium (carbon source - sugar and nitrogen source - yeast extract) from the bioreactor (working volume 4L). The cultivation parameters were monitored online (temperature 30°C, stirring rate 200-300 rpm, pH 4-5) and off line (total soluble dry matter, pH; wet cell biomass and dry cell biomass). Finally, following the post-fermentation process, a wet biomass of 46.5 g/L was obtained, respectively active dry wine yeast 14.79 g/L, which will be used in the experiments regarding the production of “Fetească regală” wines from “Pietroasa” Viticulture and Winemaking Research and Development Center, USAMV, Bucharest for assessing the terroir behavior.

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Key words: active wine dry yeast, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

THE USE OF qNMR SPECTROSCOPY FOR ANALYTICAL EVALUATION OF LAVENDER EXTRACTS. DETERMINATION OF ROSMARINIC ACID

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NMR spectroscopy is a powerful method for structural identification of both individual compounds and complex natural products mixtures. The main advantages of this modern analytical tool are, among others, high resolution power, as well as simultaneous qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the investigated sample [1].

The current work presents the determination of rosmarinic acid (RA) content in lavender extracts basing on fast and reliable 2D NMR correlations. Few data on the quantitative determination of RA in lavender are known in the literature, even though it is an abundant and highly valuable secondary metabolite [2]. A pure sample of RA was isolated from dried leaves of lemon balm (*Melissa officinalis L.*) and its ¹H and HSQC spectra recorded. Purity grade of the obtained sample was calculated basing on ¹H NMR and internal standard (IS) method. Methyl 4-nitrobenzoate was used as an IS, both for ¹H and HSQC measurements. Two diagnostic signals of RA have been chosen on the basis of their separation from the IS peaks. The HSQC relaxation delay parameter (D₁) was optimized basing on the relaxation times T₁ determined for both diagnostic signals. The calibration curve was drawn on the basis of HSQC correlation, plotting the peak volumes of the chosen diagnostic peak, normalized to the peak volume of IS versus molar ratio between RA and IS. A perfect linearity was achieved. The quantitative determination of RA in a lavender extract was easily performed, thanks to an excellent resolution of RA diagnostic signals from all other extract components cross peaks. The elaborated method can be routinely used for the quality control of herbal pharmaceuticals or related products. The analysis time is comparable with the time of an average HPLC experiment. The sample preparation procedure and interpretation of results are very simple and can be easily adapted for any modern analytical laboratory.

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Key words: diagnostic peak, NMR spectroscopy, rosmarinic acid, quality control, quantitative method.

SELECTIVE EXTRACTION OF POLYPHENOLIC COMPOUNDS FROM *HIPPOPHAE RHAMNOIDES* SEEDS

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The antioxidant properties of natural products are generally connected with the content of polyphenolic compounds, which can efficiently quench active free radicals and diminish oxidative stress of the living cells. This is very important both for maintaining and amelioration of cellular function and regarded as a relevant tool in wound tissue repair [1]. The oil obtained from the sea buckthorn (*Hippophae Rhamnoides*) represents a relevant remedy used in folk medicine for wound healing [2]. We report in the current communication the selective preparation of a polyphenol – rich extract from sea buckthorn seeds which are primarily used for oil production. The total content of phenolic compounds in the obtained extract was determined by Folin-Ciocalteu method against both galic and chlorogenic acids as standards. The high free radical scavenging ability was determined basing on the DPPH antioxidant assay. The cell-proliferation properties have been investigated by *in vitro* MTT tests on mesenchymal stem cells from rabbit bone marrow. The elaborated preparation method is simple and can be up-scaled for large production and following pre-clinical studies.

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Key words: antioxidant, buckthorn seeds, DPPH antioxidant assay, extraction, *Hippophae rhamnoides*, method, polyphenolic compounds.

STOPPED-FLOW STUDIES OF THE INTERACTION OF DFH₄ AND ITS DERIVATIVES WITH DPPH[•]

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In the course of this research, ascorbic acid, dihydroxyfumaric acid (DFH₄) and ten of its newly obtained derivatives were investigated in the modified DPPH[•] assay using the stopped-flow method.

Fig.1. shows five most potent antioxidants synthesized from DFH₄.

Obtained curves demonstrate the existence of three types of kinetic behaviors: fast, mixed (the fast stage is followed by a slower stage, which can be visually distinguished) and slow kinetic behavior.

The kinetics is determined both by the molecular structure of the studied compound and by the stability of the antioxidant radical formed following the reaction with DPPH[•].

Ascorbic acid is the only compound exhibiting rapid reaction with the radical, which is determined by the presence of two functional groups which allow the rapid transfer of hydrogen atoms.

Analysis of the obtained kinetic curves shows that DFH₄, ester 2, acid 12 and diol 13 (Fig.1) show mixed kinetics. Upon interaction with DPPH[•], a rapid decrease in radical concentration is observed in the first 3-10 seconds (1 min for ester 2), but the steady state is reached in a longer time (several minutes), compared to ascorbic acid.

Anilide 5 and fumaramide 6 exhibit a slow kinetics in the DPPH[•] assay, with a reaction time of 45-60 minutes.

Key words: antioxidant, buckthorn seeds, DPPH[•] antioxidant assay, extraction, *Hippophae rhamnoides*, method, polyphenolic compounds.

2

dimethyl 2,3-dihydroxifumarate

5

(E)-methyl 2,3-dihydroxy-4-oxo-4-(phenylamino)but-2-enoate

6

2,3-dihydroxy-N¹,N⁴-di(pyridin-2-yl)fumaramide

12

(E)-3-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)-2,3-dihydroxiacrylic acid

13

(E)-1,2-di(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)ethene-1,2-diol

Fig.1. Most potent obtained derivatives of DFH₄

ESTIMATION OF ADMET PROPERTIES OF DFH4 AND ITS NOVEL DERIVATIVES

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Computer assisted prediction of absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity (ADMET) was performed using the SwissADME online tool, for the dihydroxyfumaric acid (DFH₄) and its synthesized derivatives, which showed good antiradical activities in previous studies (Fig. 1).

The colored part of the radar shows the desired physico-chemical surface suitable for oral bioavailability of the compound: LIPO (lipofilicity): $-0,7 < XLOGP3 < +5,0$; SIZE: $150\text{g/mol} < \text{molecular weight} < 500\text{g/mol}$; POLAR (polarity): $20\text{\AA}^2 < \text{TPSA} < 130\text{\AA}^2$; INSOLU (insolubility): $-6 < \log S (\text{ESOL}) < 0$; INSATU (insaturation): $0,25 < \text{ration of sp}^3 \text{ C atoms} < 1$; FLEX (flexibility): $0 < \text{number of rotatable bonds} < 9$.

All studied compounds satisfy *Lipiski's* rule of five, and have a good estimated bioavailability (0,56), while Fig.1. also shows a good drug-likeness.

Fig.1. Bioavailability radars for the studied compounds.

Key words: dihydroxyfumaric acid, DPPH• assay, functional groups, newly obtained derivatives, kinetic behaviors.

CAROTENOID CONTENT IN PLANT PRODUCTS OF *CASSIA OCCIDENTALIS* (L.) LINK SPECIES

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The genus *Cassia* contains about 60 species, including *C. angustifolia*, known as medicinal plant. In recent decades the other species *C. occidentalis* has become the object of phytochemical studies, which allowed the identification of various chemical compounds with therapeutic effects such as anthraquinones, phenolic compounds, and carotenoids. This species was introduced into the Collection of Medicinal and Aromatic plants of the Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection of the Republic of Moldova.

Objective of the study was the determination of carotenoid content in different vegetal products collected from the *C. occidentalis* species, grown in climate conditions of the Republic of Moldova.

Carotenoid dosing was performed at *Metertech* UV/VIS SP 8001 spectrophotometer (absorbance 448 nm) in different plant products – *Folia*, *Flores*, *Fruits* and *Herba* of *C. occidentalis* species. Extraction was carried out in 2 extractants (95% ethyl alcohol and hexane) on a water bath at 60°C. Content was expressed as mg% FW.

The experimental data denote that, for all analyzed vegetal products, the extraction of carotenoids in 95% ethyl alcohol was more efficient than in hexane. The obtained results show that total carotenoids in recalculation to β -carotene varies in the analyzed plant products from 18.48 to 88.10 mg% in 95% ethyl alcohol and from 2.09 to 28.7 mg% in hexane extractant. The highest values recorded in both extractants were reported for *Folia* – 88.00 mg% in 95% ethyl alcohol and 28.70 mg% in hexane, followed by *Flores* (respectively) – 58.82 and 18.47 mg% and *Herba* – 55.23 and 17.17, but the lowest in *Fructus* 18.48 and 2.09 mg%.

Ethyl alcohol 95% is much more effective than hexane for extracting carotenoids from all plant products of *C. occidentalis* species. All analyzed plant products are characterized by carotenoid content and are of interest for the cultivation and valorization of this species for pharmaceutical purposes.

Acknowledgments: This study was carried out with the support of the project "Diminishing the consequences of climate change by creating, implementing varieties of medicinal and aromatic plants with high productivity, resistant to drought, wintering, disease, ensuring sustainable development of agriculture, guarantees high quality products, predestined for the industry perfumery, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, food ", code 20.80009.5107.07

Key words: antiradical activities, bioavailability, dihydroxyfumaric acid, SwissADME, synthesized derivatives.

CONTENT OF TANNINS IN PLANT PRODUCTS OF SOME SPECIES FROM GENUS ACTINIDIA

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The genus *Actinidia*, native to the temperate eastern Asia, contains about 80 species. Many species of this genus have interes for pharmacy, food, green space ornamentation and cosmetics. Plant products collected from 3 species – *A. kolomikta* (Rupr. & Maxim), *A. argura* (Siebold & Zucc.) Planchand and *A. deliciosa* (A. Chev.) C.F. Liang & A.R. Ferguson, which were introduced into the plant collection of the *Alexandru Ciubotaru* National Botanical Garden were subjected to phytochemical analysis, including tannin content.

Objective of the study was the determination of tannin content in different vegetal products collected from 3 species of genus *Actinidia*, grown in climate conditions of the Republic of Moldova.

Tannin dosing was performed by titrimetric method in different plant products – *Radices, Cortex, Folia and Fructus* of *A. kolomikta*, *A. argura* and *A. deliciosa* species. Content was expressed as % FW.

The experimental data, obtained in 3 replicates, show that all the products analyzed contain tannins, but the content varies from 0.575 to 11.361% depending on the type of plant product and species. The highest tannin values were recorded for juvenile vegetal products of *Cortex* (11.361%) and *Folia* (8.563%) from species *A. kolomikta*. For the other vegetal products such as mature leaves, roots, mature bark, fruits of *A. kolomikta* as well as the other 2 species *A. arguta* and *A. deliciosa* the tannin content ranged between 0.575 and 2.403%.

From all plant products (*Radices, Cortex, Folia, Fructus*) analyzed from 3 species of g. *Actinidia* (*A. kolomikta, A. arguta and A. deliciosa*), grown in the climate conditions of the Republic of Moldova, the juvenile leaves and bark of *A. kolomikta* species were found to have a high tannin content, which can be used for pharmaceutical purposes.

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Key words: *Actinidia sp.*, tannin content, titrimetric method, vegetal products.

**PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF CRUD EXTRACT
FROM *TANACETUM CORYMBOSUM* (L.) SHI. BIP.**

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Tanacetum corymbosum (Corymbflower tansy) is an herbaceous perennial plant growing solitary or in small groups in the spontaneous flora of the Republic of Moldova. This specie is used in digestive disorders, as antiprotozoal and antibacterial remedy. Unlike, its chemical composition is less studied and this study is a continuation of the previous works, when the elemental analysis of *T. corymbosum* plants [1], chemical composition of its essential oil and antimicrobial analysis of crud extract were reported [2].

The aim of the present research was to investigate phytochemical profile of *T. corymbosum* extract using GC-MS analysis. According to this, the chemical composition of the species is extremely varied and includes constituents of many and diverse classes of organic compounds. The aliphatic hydrocarbons are presented by higher alkanes (C₉-C₂₁), together with others cyclic, unsaturated or aromatic compounds. Also, a small number of alcohols (e.g. cetylic), aldehydes (e.g. caproic) and more numerous carboxylic acids (e.g. capric, myristic, stearic) and esters (e.g. methyl palmitate, ethyl linoleate, bornyl acetate) were detected.

However, terpene compounds determine the chemical profile of the species. The most numerous are monoterpenes, more exactly hydrocarbons (e.g. limonene, *p*-cymene) and oxygenated forms (e.g. linalool, camphor). They a followed by sesquiterpene hydrocarbons (e.g. caryophyllene, humulene) and oxygenated forms (e.g. farnesol). Other superior terpenes have been identified in smaller numbers: diterpene hydrocarbons (e.g. neophytadiene) and oxygenated forms (e.g. phytol), or triterpenes (e.g. squalene).

Based on the present investigation, we conclude that *T. corymbosum* species because of its active principles can be used for pharmaceutical purposes.

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Key words: organic compounds, phytochemical profile, *Tanacetum corymbosum*, terpene compounds.

SYNTHESIS OF N-CYCLOHEXYL-2-[(3-ETHOXY-2-HYDROXYPHENYL) METHYLIDENE] HYDRAZINE-1-CARBOTHIOAMIDE

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The recently studied thiosemicarbazones have exceeded researchers' expectations by demonstrating advanced pharmacological effects, such as anticancer, antibacterial and antioxidant effects.

The paper presents the synthesis of new ligand N-cyclohexyl-2-[(3-ethoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl) methylidene] hydrazine-1-carbothioamide (**H₂L**) obtained through the addition of 2-ethoxy-6-[hydrazinylidenemethyl] phenol to isothiocyanatocyclohexane.

Figure. Synthesis of N-cyclohexyl-2-[(3-ethoxy-2-hydroxyphenyl) methylidene] hydrazine-1-carbothioamide (**H₂L**)

i- CSCl₂, CaCO₃, H₂O, (extracts with CH₂Cl₂), 2 h;

ii- 2-ethoxy-6-[hydrazinylidenemethyl]phenol

(preferred name - hydrazone to 3-ethoxyalicylaldehyde) tetrahydrofuran, 1.5 h.

Thiosemicarbazone H₂L was characterized on the basis of various spectroscopic techniques like FTIR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR studies, elemental analysis. The compound was subjected to antimicrobial and antifungal activity screening using serial broth dilution method. The thiosemicarbazone H₂L showed moderate activity against: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Acinetobacter baumannii* and *Candida albicans*.

Key words: antifungal, antimicrobial, dilution method, pharmacological effects, thiosemicarbazone H₂L.

JINMIAO TARGET INHIBITION OF *O. CUMANA* THE MECHANISM OF PARASITIC SUNFLOWER

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Jinmiao Target is a new kind of anti broomrape induced resistant agent. It has been shown that stem and leaf spray and root drip irrigation can inhibit the parasitism of sunflower broomrape, but the mechanism is unclear. The mechanism of the inhibition of broomrape on sunflower resistant variety (JK103) and susceptible variety (LD5009) by root watering was studied. Compared with the control, the number of tubercles decreased by 95.5 and the parasitism rate decreased by 98.20% after treatment with LD5009+Jinmiao Target, the fresh weight and dry weight of tubercles decreased by 94.60% and 81.63%. The height and stem diameter of sunflower increased by 2.09 cm and 0.52 cm and the growth rates were 14.92% and 15.29%. However, the number of tubercles in the resistant variety JK103+Jinmiao Target reduced by 37.5 and the parasitism rate decreased by 98.04%, the fresh weight and dry weight of tubercles decreased by 97.06% and 82.69%. The height and stem diameter of sunflower increased by 2.07 cm and 0.39 cm and the growth rates were 12.26% and 9.70%. After irrigation the corpus callosum deposition in the roots of the resistant and susceptible cultivars was increased. However, the resistance variety JK103 showed the most significant increase after 48h.

The results showed that after root irrigation in both resistant and susceptible varieties, the content of H₂O₂ after 24h reached the maximum, 3.53μmol/g and 2.68μmol/g respectively. The most significant increase was recorded in the susceptible variety LD5009, an increase of 208.05%. The activities of four different ROS scavenging enzymes showed an initial trend of increasing and then decreasing after treatment. The maximum value was reached at 48h after JK103+Jinmiao Target treatment, the maximum values of SOD, POD, CAT and PPO were 69.77g⁻¹, 5.44g⁻¹.min⁻¹, 1.88g⁻¹.min⁻¹ and 527g⁻¹.min⁻¹ respectively. However, after LD5009+ Jinmiao Target treatment, the activities of the above four ROS scavenging enzymes were increased by 25.91g⁻¹, 13.16g⁻¹.min⁻¹, 0.50g⁻¹.min⁻¹ and 313g⁻¹.min⁻¹. Transcriptional analysis of related resistance genes indicated that the resusceptible variety was induced in different degrees after target treatment. However, induction degree of LD5009 with Jinmiao Target was the most obvious, especially *CAT*, *Mn-SOD* and *XTH6*. The relative expression levels were more than 50 times higher than the control. In conclusion, both resistant and susceptible varieties, the host resistance was induced at different levels after Jinmiao Target treatment, the degree of induction varies from cultivar to cultivar.

Key words: antibroomrape agent, Jinmiao Target, mechanism of the inhibition, resistant agent, sunflower.

STUDY OF THE ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES OF SOME METHYLPHENYLTHIOSEMICARBAZONES

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Antioxidants are important compounds that reduce or neutralize free radicals, thus protecting cells from oxidation. Considerable research has been directed towards the identification of new antioxidants to prevent radical damages.

Due to the presence of donor atoms such as N, S, the thiosemicarbazide backbone has been extensively studied over the last 70 years. Therefore numerous thiosemicarbazide derivatives as substituted thiosemicarbazones at N (4) and N (1) of aliphatic, aromatic and heteroaromatic carbonyl compounds were synthesized and evaluated for antitumor, antimicrobial, cytotoxic and antioxidant activity.

In order to supplement the data on agents with potential biological activity, three N4-n-methylphenylthiosemicarbazides were synthesized, and subsequently condensed with 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (o-vanillin). The antioxidant activity of the compounds was then evaluated by analysis of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl DPPH and 2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazole-6-sulfonic acid) ABTS and compared with that of trolox.

From the results obtained from the antioxidant activity of the synthesized compounds it can be concluded that the introduction of a substituent such as the phenyl group at N (4), in the thiosemicarbazide backbone, leads to biologically active compounds. The antioxidant properties are amplified with the substitution at N (1), by introducing the carbonyl fragment. All the synthesized compounds showed higher values than the control sample, against the radical cations ABTS and the radical DHHP. They are in the next phase of testing for use as medicines.

No	Name of new compounds	ABTS•+ radical cation scavenging activity IC ₅₀ , μM/L	DPPH• radical scavenging activity IC ₅₀ , μM/L
1	<i>N</i> -(2-methylphenyl) hydrazinecarbothioamide	16,2	32,1
	2-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)- <i>N</i> -(2-methylphenyl) hydrazinecarbothioamide	15,2	12,6
2	<i>N</i> -(2,4-dimethylphenyl) hydrazinecarbothioamide	15,3	34,2
	2-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)- <i>N</i> -(2,4-dimethylphenyl) hydrazinecarbothioamide	11,2	28,5
3	<i>N</i> -(2,4,6-trimethylphenyl) hydrazinecarbothioamide	14,4	31,4
	2-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)- <i>N</i> -(2,4,6-trimethylphenyl) hydrazinecarbothioamide	11,8	43,8
4	Trolox/ control sample	26,3	48,9

Key words: antioxidant properties, DPPH• radical scavenging activity, free radicals, N4-n-methylphenylthiosemicarbazides.

NATURAL DYES FROM POKEWEEED BERRIES: EXTRACTION PROCEDURES AND STABILITY

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Natural dyes extracted from berries of pokeweed (*Phytolacca americana*) were used as colorants in food and textile industries because of their nontoxic and ecofriendly characteristics, as nutraceuticals with antioxidant properties and sensitizers for dye-sensitized solar cells. Chemical structure of natural dyes from pokeweed berries belong to the betalains class, namely to betacyanins that provide the red-violet color and betaxanthins with yellow-orange color. Complexity of betalains extraction consist in poor stability of natural dyes and depends on various factors (temperature, pH, and concentration of dye, water activity, light and UV radiation, metal chelators, mordant and pretreatment of raw materials). The purpose of this work was to describe the different approaches to optimize the extraction technique for obtaining the natural dyes from pokeweed berries in stable form based on previous researches. The cheapest methods of dyes obtaining is extraction using different solvent systems (water-alcoholic, weak acid solutions, buffer solutions, etc.) by liquid-solid extraction in ratio 5:1. Our studies were shown that water extracts from pokeweed berries contained 5.5 times more betalain colorants when compared to ethyl alcohol (95%) extracts. While it is necessary to take into account that colorants from pokeweed maintain the stability in limits of pH from 3.0 to 7.0. The optimal pH for maximum stability of betalains is 5-6. To enhance the betalain extraction yields, the different methods of pretreatment were proposed, such as pulsed electric fields, gamma irradiation, and low-direct current electric fields, ultrasonic or microwave assisted extractions. Their advantages consist in processing at low temperatures due to the high sensitivity of betalains to heat, which decompose at temperatures above 50°C. However, in our studies it was determined that the concentration of natural dyes in pokeweed berries did not change during the year of storage at a temperature of -12-16°C. Encapsulation of extracted betalains with polysaccharides (pectin, guar gum) as the wall material led to increased stability and longer shelf life of natural dyes. Based on the described approaches and our data, the developed technological procedure for obtaining and stabilizing of natural dyes from pokeweed berries will be proposed for patenting as a food colorant.

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Key words: betalains, extraction technique, natural dyes, optimal pH, *Phytolacca americana*, stabilizing, obtaining.

SYNTHESIS OF NEW POTENTIAL ACTIVE HOMODRIMANE SESQUITERPENOIDS WITH BENZIMIDAZOLE FRAGMENT

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Sesquiterpenoids, including those with a homodrimane skeleton, are natural compounds with a wide range of biological activities. Furthermore, the benzimidazole and its derivatives are considered interesting heterocycles since they possess important pharmacological activities. For this reason, synthesis of terpene compounds with heterocyclic fragments, especially benzimidazoles is a perspective direction of research in the field of biologically active compounds.

As starting material for the synthesis of title compounds 11-homodrim-6(7),8(9)-dien-12-oic acid **2a**, 7 α -methoxy-11-homodrim-8(9)-en-12-oic acid **2b** and 11-homodrim-8(9)-en-12-oic acid **2c**, previously obtained from commercial (+)-sclareolide **1** in 5, 3 and 5 steps, were used. After that, two methods of synthesis were proposed. The first method consists of interactions of one of the acids **2a,b** with *o*-phenylenediamine in the presence of triphenylphosphine (Ph₃P) and triethylamine (Et₃N), giving desired compounds **4a,b**. The second method includes the interaction of 2-aminobenzimidazole with one of the acid chlorides **3a-c** generated *in situ* from acids **2a-c**, giving desired compounds **5a-c** (Scheme).

The structure of all obtained compounds has been established using modern methods of analysis (ATR-FTIR, ¹H, ¹³C and ¹⁵N RMN spectroscopy).

Scheme. Synthesis of terpeno-benzimidazole hybrid compounds.

Reagents and conditions: a. *o*-Phenylenediamine, Ph₃P, Et₃N, CCl₄, Δ , 4h, 46-57%.
b. (COCl)₂, C₆H₆, r.t. 1h, Δ , 1h; c. 2-Aminobenzimidazole, CH₂Cl₂, r.t. 3h, Δ , 4h, 49-85%.

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Key words: biologically active compounds, methods of synthesis, pharmacological activities, sesquiterpenoids.

IRON(III) CLUSTERS WITH 3-FORMYLSALICYLIC ACID

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In the presence of additional ligands and polar solvents, the well-known μ_3 -oxo bridged triangular iron carboxylates easily reorganize and stabilize large complexes. We chose 3-formylsalicylic acid (H_2L) in order to explore its coordinative ability, due to its multiple coordination donor groups like $-COOH$, $-OH$ and $-CHO$. Herein, new hexanuclear iron(III) clusters $[Fe_6O_2(OH)_2(L)_2(H_2O)_2(O_2CR)_8] \cdot MeCN$ ($R = CMe_3$ (**1**); $CHMe_2$ (**2**)), where L is the dianion of 3-formylsalicylic acid, are reported. Compounds **1** and **2** were prepared from the reaction of μ_3 -oxo trinuclear iron(III) precursors $[Fe_3(\mu_3-O)(H_2O)_3(O_2CR)_6](O_2CR) \cdot 2HO_2CR$ with 3-formylsalicylic acid in acetonitrile. Both structures comprise six Fe atoms in an almost planar arrangement that can be described as two oxo-centered triangular units $[Fe_3(\mu_3-O)]^{7+}$ joined together by two bridging hydroxide and two bridging carboxylate groups. The asymmetric units contain only half of an Fe_6 molecule. All Fe atoms adopt distorted octahedral coordination geometries and are in the +3 oxidation state. The peripheral ligation of metal ions is completed by six carboxylate molecules and two aldehyde ligands which are in their monoanionic and dianionic forms, respectively. The two 3-formylsalicylic ligands act as tridentate, bridging $Fe1$ ($Fe1'$) and $Fe2$ ($Fe2'$) ions by the alkoxo groups within each $[Fe_3(\mu_3-O)]^{7+}$ unit. The oxygen atom of the formyl group is also coordinated, which was not reported so far for this ligand. All carboxylate groups adopt the bridging μ_2 - η^1 : η^1 coordination mode: two of them join the edges of the triangular $[Fe_3(\mu_3-O)]^{7+}$ units and the remaining six link Fe atoms within the latters (Fig. 1). Detailed characterization of compounds **1** and **2** will be described in a forthcoming paper.

Figure 1. The molecular structure of complex **2**· CH_3CN (left) and its $[Fe_6(\mu_3-O)_2(\mu-OH)_2]^{12+}$ structural core (right). Color code: Fe^{III} , olive green; O, red; C, grey. The hydrogen atoms, methyl groups and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity.

Key words: 3-formylsalicylic acid, asymmetric units, hexanuclear iron(III) clusters, peripheral ligation.

SYNTHESIS OF SOME THIOSEMICARBAZONES DERIVED FROM 1-PYRIDIN-2-YL-3-PHENYL-PROP-2-EN-1-ONES (CHALCONES) SUBSTITUTED IN THE PHENYL RING

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Thiosemicarbazones are organosulfur compounds with the general formula $H_2NC(S)NHN=CRR$, which possess a wide spectrum of medicinal properties, they are studied for their antibacterial, antiviral and antifungal activities. Because of these activities thiosemicarbazones have been clinically tested for a variety of diseases, such as tuberculosis, viral infections, malaria and cancer. Also, their complexes with metals show a wide range of biological activities. Chalcones or 1,3-diarylprop-2-en-1-ones belong to the flavonoid family, in which the aryl rings are linked by an α - β unsaturated ketone moiety. Their wide distribution in nature, as well as the simple methods of synthesis and the accessibility of the precursors has always encouraged the investigation of the possibilities of their application in medicine due to their activity: antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antimalarial, antitumor. Although there is a multitude of thiosemicarbazones in the literature, those derived from chalcones are very little studied. And the known structures show serious potential to be studied as biologically active substances.

Thiosemicarbazones of chalcones were obtained by the following method (Figure 1): to the molar equivalent of chalcone and thiosemicarbazide diluted in alcohol, a few drops of HCl are added to catalyze the reaction. The reaction mixture is vigorously stirred for 2-3 hours at temperatures between 35-45°C. The obtained solids were filtered and dried to be subjected to their physical and chemical studies. The yields are between 50-80%.

Fig. 1

The listed chalcones were obtained by aldol condensation (Fig.2) which is a synthesis within the field of green chemistry, where a solution of NaOH or Na_2CO_3 is added dropwise to the mixture of 2-acetylpyridine and the appropriate aldehyde in alcohol. The reaction mixture is stirred from 1 to 6 hours at room temperature. A solid is obtained, which is filtered, washed with water, then recrystallized from alcohol.

Fig. 2

I. R¹=R⁴=OCH₃ II. R²=R³=OCH₃ III. R²=R³=R⁴OCH₃

Key words: Aldol condensation, biological activities, medicinal properties, thiosemicarbazones, synthesis.

MICROMORPHOLOGICAL AND ANATOMICAL CHANGES INDUCED BY SALINE STRESS IN *OCIMUM BASILICUM* L. (VAR. GENOVESE), IN EXPERIMENTAL GROWTH CONDITIONS

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Today, saline stress is a major concern in the agricultural field, generating numerous research. Increased salinity inhibits the uptake of nutrients by plants and decreases water quality, causing ionic toxicity, nutritional disorders and osmotic stress and limits agricultural production, thus becoming a global problem^{1,2,3,4,5}. The present study aims at the adaptation and resistance of basil to different degrees of salinity, a taxon of interest in research to identify plants capable of supporting and developing in conditions of high salinity^{3,6,7}. The biological material used in the experiment was obtained from basil seeds, *Ocimum basilicum* L. (var. Genovese), purchased commercially, grown under experimental laboratory conditions.

A peat-based substrate was used for germination, and when the plant individuals reached dimensions of about 4 cm, they were transplanted into pots with universal soil, the saline treatment being applied after the appearance of the first true leaves.

After consulting the literature, in the present experiment were used 3 concentrations of sodium chloride, considered high concentrations for plant cultivation: 100 mM, 150 mM and 200 mM, the saline solutions being administered in 3 repetitions. At the end of the cultivation interval, micro-morphological and anatomical determinations were performed at the root, hypocotyl, epicotyl and leaves, to identify any morphological and structural changes caused to these organs by artificially induced saline stress.

Micro-morphological analyses showed, at the level of the lower and upper surface of the leaves, a decrease in the number of secretory hairs with the increase of the salt concentration in the cultivation substrate. At the same time, the number of stomata showed a similar evolution, but it was observed that, with the decrease of the number of stomata (more accentuated effect at high NaCl concentrations), their surface area increased. From an anatomical point of view, an increase in the number of conducting vessels was observed in plants grown on substrate with high concentrations of NaCl. At the root level, a premature suberification was observed, a phenomenon that leads to the loss of water absorption properties and is also confirmed by the increased number of secondary roots formed. This can be interpreted as a response of test plants to physiological drought caused by experimentally induced saline stress⁸.

The ability of basil to respond to saline stress and counteract its effects through various defence mechanisms make this taxon a potential candidate for cultivation on saline soils.

Further investigations are needed at different stages of plant development, to obtain a clearer picture of the effects of salinity on the development and adaptation of basil to conditions of saline stress.

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Key words: stomata, *Ocimum basilicum*, physiological drought, resistance, saline stress, suberification.

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF DAMASK ROSE (*ROSA DAMASCENA* MILL.) CONCRETE OF MOLDAVIAN ORIGIN

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The Damask rose (*Rosa damascena* Mill.) is an important aromatic plant and one of the most important rose species used for commercial production of rose essential oil, rose water, concrete and absolute. These products are widely used in perfumery and cosmetics, foodstuffs, as well as in pharmaceutical industry. It was reported, that individual rose products or some rose preparations possess antimicrobial, antioxidant, relaxant, anti-inflammatory, insecticidal, anti-HIV and hypnotic properties, and are frequently used for treatment various diseases [1-3].

The main World producers are Bulgaria and Turkey, followed by France, Italy, Ukraine, Russia, Morocco, Egypt, Libya, Iran, China and India. In the former USSR, Moldova was the major producer among the Soviet republics. Currently, here are only a few small growers and rose processing plants [1-3].

The chemical composition of rose essential oil and rose water has been well studied. In opposite, the rose concrete composition is less studied. For this reason, herein the chemical composition of rose concrete of Moldavian origin is reported.

The concrete was obtained industrially in 2020 by extracting freshly collected rose petals (Pervomaisc village, Causeni district) with petroleum ether followed by complete distillation of the solvent under reduced pressure. Its overall yield was of about 0,2% recalculated for starting material. Next, the concrete was subjected to GC-MS analysis on an Agilent 7890B system, equipped with VF-WAXms 30m x 250µm x 0.25µm column during 30 minutes.

About 44 constituents of rose concrete, which belong to several groups of compounds were identified. The major constituents are as follows: monoterpene alcohols - citronellol (2.06%), nerol (2.99%) and geraniol (5.62%); monoterpene pyrans - rose oxides (0.44%); higher hydrocarbons: nonadecane (1.26%), heneicosane (1.78%), tricosane (3.09%) and aromatic alcohol 2-phenylethyl alcohol (60.42%).

The rose concrete is a valuable substance, and the quality of the product that can be obtained from Moldovan plantations should be maintained and controlled.

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Key words: Chemical composition, citronellol, extracting, geraniol, nerol, *Rosa damascene*, rose essential oil.

SYNTHESIS AND STUDY OF Zn TETRA-SUBSTITUTED PHTHALOCYANINE WITH CHALCONIC GROUPS

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The chalcones are considered derivatives of flavonoids and izoflavonoids, which have in their structure aromatic rings connected through a fragment of prop-2-en-1-one. The modification of aromatic rings by different heterocyclic rings creates a wide variety of new substances with a large spectrum of properties which can be used in pharmaceutical industry and the production of new medicines. The possibility to play with the chalcones structures favors the obtaining of pharmaceutical products with low toxicity and high pharmacological action [1]. The chalcones are spread in plants and possess a wide spectrum of uses, due to their antioxidants properties, antibacterial, antifungal, insecticides and anticancer [2].

The antimicrobial resistance is one of the most important threats for our health. This requires efforts to discover new ways to completely eliminate these microbial pathogens. The use of photosensitizers and light is a complementary way to fight against pathogenic microbes. Nowadays, the metalphthalocyanines are intensively studied due to their structures which are rich in π conjugated systems, and have potential applications in various technological areas as optoelectronic devices, gas sensors, static induction transistors and photo receptors in laser beam printers [3].

In the literature are described a series of chalconic derivatives transformed into complexes with non-transitional metals. This type of products is widely studied by the fact that they possess more functional groups which allow the chemical connection with metals, modifying in this way the spectral and medicinal properties.

Also, are known synthesis methods of Zn and Co(II) metalphthalocyanines which have as substituents chalconic fragments. These products are obtained through the following steps: a) synthesis of chalcones with $-OH$ groups by Claisen-Schmidt method, using the KOH as a base and ethanol as solvent; b) the interaction of the respective chalcones with 4-nitrophthalonitrile in the presence of K_2CO_3 , nitrogen atmosphere and DMSO for obtaining tetrasubstituted phthalocyanine with chalconic fragments; c) treatment of tetrasubstituted phthalocyanine which contains chalconic fragments with $ZnCl_2$ and $CoCl_2$ salts to give metalphthalocyanines and as catalyst is used the N,N -dimethylethanolamine [4].

The aim of this study is the synthesis of Zn tetrasubstituted phthalocyanine with chalconic groups by the following scheme:

Zn Tetranitrophthalocyanine (1) was synthesized from 4-nitrophthalonitrile. The formed mixture of 4-nitrophthalonitrile, $Zn(CH_3COO)_2$ and DBU (1,8-diazabicyclo [5.4] undec-7-ene) was refluxed in pentan-1-ol for 8 hours. For purification (1) is treated with HCl (5%) at the temperature of 95 °C for 30 min. Zn tetranitrophthalocyanine (1) is treated with Na_2S aqueous solution to give Zn tetraaminophthalocyanine (2). The purity of (2) was verified by thin layer chromatography on silica gel, eluent chloroform: tetrahydrofuran 6:1 [5]. 3-(4-Dimethylamino) phenyl-1-(4-isothiocyanatophenyl) prop-2-en-1-one was synthesized from 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and 4-isothiocyanatoacetophenone, as catalyst concentrated HCl at 45 °C for 2 hours [6]. The presence of $-NH_2$ group in (2) gives the opportunity to chemically connect the 3-(4-dimethylamino) phenyl-1-(4-isothiocyanatophenyl) prop-2-en-1-one (3) with Zn tetraaminophthalocyanine (2) to give tetrasubstituted Zn phthalocyanine with chalconic groups. The reaction mixture formed from 3-(4-dimethylamino) phenyl-1-(4-isothiocyanatophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (3) and Zn tetraaminophthalocyanine (2) 4:1 ratio, is

dissolved in DMF and heated to 60-65 °C for 5 hours. The reaction product is obtained with a yield of 57%. For obtained compounds IR analysis was performed.

Fig. 1. Synthesis of Zn tetra-substituted phthalocyanine with chalconic groups

The synthesis of one Zn tetrasubstitutedphthalocyanine with chalconic groups was realized and the presence of functional groups was confirmed by IR spectra. These types of compounds can be used as fluorescent substances. The fluorescent characteristics are due to the presence of chalconic groups.

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Key words: antimicrobial resistance, chalcones, pharmaceutical industry, Zn tetrasubstitutedphthalocyanine.

DESIGNING OF THE BEST SLEEP PROTOCOL ACCORDING TO THE PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL NEED

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While many of us think of sleep as a stretch of time where nothing happens, sleep is actually, at least neurologically. Although the importance of sleep cannot be disputed, scientists do not know exactly why so important to our survival. A rested body is much stronger and can defend itself better against infections and colds. Chronic sleep deprivation can lead to long-term mood disorders, such as depression and anxiety. Scientists have found that people who usually sleep less than 5 hours a night have an increased risk of developing diabetes. Lack of deep sleep changes the way the body produces glucose. Increases sexual appetite and decreases the risk of heart disease. Lack of sleep for long periods of time is associated with an increased level of blood pressure, rhythm increased heart rate and higher levels of certain chemicals that increase the risk of inflammation.

Considering literature data indicating psychophysiological variations during and due to sleep, the studying methods for this experiment are:

1. Surveys and psychological tests.
2. Polysomnography.
3. Hormone levels lab results.

A survey concludes that people who sleep less of 6 hours a night, or sleeping more than 9 hours, had a 30% higher death rate than those who usually sleep 7 - 8 hours. Even those who slept less than 6 hours and generally did not had health problems but had a 1.8 times higher death rate than those who slept "normal" hours.

In January 2017, a study was made public according to which insufficient sleep exposes the body to diseases by weakening the immune system.

The immune system works best when has enough sleep. Seven or more hours of rest are recommended for optimal health. Adolescents, in March 2016, showed that one in ten children are at risk of breathing disorders in sleep time. 9.6% of children in Romania are at risk for breathing disorders during sleep, of which the most severe form is obstructive sleep apnea. Children who are at risk for this problem can have signs during the night or during the day.

Humans have an internal circadian rhythm, a routine and behavioral processes that occur approximately every day for 24 hours. Despite this fact, what is the right time for a person to sleep, we know which one is the best and healthier type of sleep for a person's overall health.

Key words: behavioral processes, circadian rhythm, disorders, optimal health, sleep protocol.

COPPER COMPLEXES WITH N⁴(2-ETHYL BENZOATE) THIOSEMICARBAZONE OF 2-ACETILPYRIDINE

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Thiosemicarbazones are an important class of organic compounds that have attracted attention in the pharmaceutical industry due to their high biological activity such as antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, antimalarial, antitumor and others.

The paper presents the synthesis of new ligand and coordination compounds of Cu(II), with N⁴(2-ethyl benzoate) thiosemicarbazone of 2-acetylpyridine (**3**) obtained through the addition of ethyl 2-isothiocyanatobenzoate (**2**) with 2-(1-hydrazinylideneethyl)pyridine.

Fig. 1. Synthesis of N⁴(2-ethyl benzoate) thiosemicarbazone of 2-acetylpyridine (**3**)

Based on the synthesized thiosemicarbazone HL, five coordination compounds were obtained by mixing, the salts of Cu(II) solutions in ethanol and ligand solutions in ethanol ratio of 1:1, reflux for half an hour. Obtained as a green microcrystalline complexes according to the reaction written below.

The characterization of new compounds was done by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, IR spectroscopy, conductivity and elemental analysis. In addition, the structures of the ligand (HL) and complexes [Cu(L)NO₃], [Cu(L)H₂O]₂·2ClO₄·4H₂O were determined by single-crystal X-ray diffraction.

Fig. 2. Crystalline structure of ligand (HL), coordination compound [Cu(L)NO₃] and [Cu(L)H₂O]₂·2ClO₄·4H₂O

The effect of ligand and complexes on antioxidant activity were studied. The best result was found to be on ligand, with IC₅₀ = 22.51 μM, it is better than the substance Trolox, IC₅₀ = 33.33 μM used in medicine.

Key words: antioxidant activity, thiosemicarbazones, new compounds, IR spectroscopy, synthesis of new ligand.

AUTOPHAGY ROLE IN MODULATING INFLAMMATORY MARKERS RESPONSE IN KERATINOCYTES

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Autophagy is involved in a wide range of cellular physiological processes, including the response immune, tumorigenesis, differentiation, apoptosis, antimicrobial defense, etc. Impaired autophagy is associated with a wide range of human diseases, such as diseases neurodegenerative, cardiomyopathies, infectious diseases and cancers, and autophagy modulation was already considered a potential target for the therapy of these diseases.

Modulation of the autophagy mechanism could be a better strategy than inhibition of melanin synthesis or transfer for treating disorders of skin pigmentation. Moreover, inhibition of autophagy increased significantly accumulation of p62, expression cathelicidin/LL-37 and inflammatory cytokine production. The effects of autophagy on chronic skin disorders will be studied, the everyday factors that modulates the immune response in epithelial cells and possible therapeutic alternatives in expression of inflammatory markers in keratinocytes under the action of autophagy mechanisms, induced by fasting and pharmacological simulation.

Considering literature data indicating the anti-inflammatory action of some medicinal plants, the studying methods for this experimental study are:

1. Obtaining aqueous and hydroalcoholic plant extracts.
2. UV-Vis spectrophotometric analysis of the extracts and determination of the content in phenolic compounds.

Studying the role of autophagy in the human body and the mechanisms which it participates in, such as the evolution of tumors. The obtained results demonstrate that in the initial stage in the process of oncogenesis, autophagy has the role of tumor growth suppressor, however, in the late stage a oncogenesis, contributes to the development of the tumor process by providing the cells with a substrate for synthesis of ATP and macromolecules, inhibiting anoikis. Respectively, mutations in a number of genes from the reaction cascade of the autophagy involve expression products that are indispensable. Currently, have been discovered chemicals capable of activating/inhibiting autophagy activity.

Developing new positive modulators of autophagy opens a new perspective in making more effective remedies for fighting chronic skin diseases.

Key words: autophagy, mechanism, modulators of autophagy, tumor growth suppressor.

OPTIMIZATION OF THE EXTRACTION PROCESS OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS FROM PEACHES

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Peach fruits have long been promoted for their ability to prevent various diseases, due to phytochemicals that include carotenoids, phenolic acids, organic acids, micro- and macroelements. In the Republic of Moldova, peach fruits are widely used both fresh and for processing in order to obtain a wide range of canned products. Pomace obtained as a result of peach processing, is rich in polyphenols, tannins, aromatic substances, etc., is of interest for subsequent exploitation in the food industry. The aim of this paper is to optimize the extraction process of bioactive substances from peach pomace in order to obtain the extract for use in the formulation of novel foods with high biological value.

Peach pulp dried at a temperature of 60 ± 1 °C and ground to a granularity of 70μ was used for research. To determine the optimal volume of solvent for the extraction of water-soluble compounds, distilled water, ethyl alcohol 96 % (v/v) and 50 % (v/v) hydroalcoholic solution were used. The extraction was performed at a temperature of 70 ± 2 °C with different volumes: 8, 12, 16, 20, 24 mL. The water-soluble substance content of the extract was determined by the refractometric method. The extraction of water-soluble substances was performed until the equilibrium concentration was reached. In the extracts obtained at optimal volumes of solvent, the total polyphenol content (TPC) was determined by the Folin Ciocalteu method, and the antioxidant activity (AA) of the extracts was assessed by reaction with the radical DPPH.

The results of the research showed that the best extraction in water took place when applying the solvent volume of 12 mL, in the case of the hydroalcoholic extractant of 50% (v/v) the most effective was the volume of 20 mL, and in the alcoholic solvent of 96% (v/v) - the volume of 16 mL was the most efficient. The study of the extraction kinetics of water-soluble substances from peach pomace showed that the degree of extraction is higher at first, later showing a slowing trend. Distilled water has been shown to contribute to better tissue separation and rupture of cell walls of peach pulp, facilitating the diffusion of water-soluble compounds. It was found that solvents have a major influence on the TPC, as follows: the lowest polyphenol content was recorded in the case of extraction in ethyl alcohol 96% (v/v), with a value of 13.84 mg GAE/g plant. In the case of 50% hydroalcoholic solution and distilled water, TPC increased approximately 6.4 times. It is known that polyphenols are responsible for the antioxidant activity in plant extracts. It has been shown that the extracts with the highest TPC are characterized by the highest value of AA. In the case of our extracts the AA varies between 63.69 % (ethyl alcohol of 96% (v/v)) and 71.13% - 50% (v/v) hydroalcoholic solution. Thus, it has been shown that the type of solvent can influence the extraction yield of polyphenolic compounds and antioxidant activity.

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Key words: bioactive substances, extraction process, food industry, peaches.

Cu(II) COMPLEXES WITH 1,5-BIS(2-HYDROXY-3-METHOXYBENZYLIDENE) CARBOHYDRAZIDE**Talmaci Natalia***Institute of Chemistry, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova*E-mail: tnatalia.andrei@mail.ru

This communications shows that the nature of anions of the corresponding copper salts, as well as their coordination properties are essential in determining the final structures of the complexes with the ligand 1,5-bis(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene) carbohydrazide (H₄L). Thus, by its interaction with copper(II) chloride, binuclear compound [Cu₂(H₂L_{cycl})(CH₃OH)₂Cl₂]-CH₃OH (**1**), was obtained, where cyclization of the thiocarbohydrazone ligand occurs with the formation of a 1,3,4-thiadiazole ring. It should be mentioned that the methoxy group plays the role of a bridge between copper ions [1]. By the interaction of the same ligand with copper(II) acetate in DMSO, octanuclear complex [Cu₈L(DMSO)₈] (**2**) was prepared. The organic ligand keeps its original form, but it is totally deprotonated, behaving as a tetrabasic acid, and the methoxy group is not involved into coordination. The composition and the structure of compound **2** was determined using elemental analysis, IR spectroscopy and single crystal X-ray diffraction study. In the complex **2** it can be highlighted the neutral binuclear unit Cu₂L composed of the bicompartamental ligand that hosts two copper ions. A nitrogen atom of this fragment is located in the coordination sphere of another copper atom of the adjacent dimeric fragment. As a result, all 7 donor atoms of the organic reagent are involved in coordination, forming an octanuclear metalomacrocyclic compound. Among four independent copper(II) ions, two from the ONS donor atoms set have a square planar geometry, while the coordination polyhedra of another two from the ONN donor atoms set can be described as a distorted trigonal bipyramid.

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Key words: copper salts, crystal X-ray diffraction, methoxy group, 1,5-bis(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene, IR spectroscopy.

CU(II) COMPLEXES WITH 4-ALLYLTHIOSEMICARBAZONE AS POSSIBLE ANTIOXIDANT AGENTS

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Oxidation is an essential part of aerobic metabolism in living organisms. In this process, free radicals are constantly generated. It is widely known that free radicals play a dual role *in vivo* as both beneficial and adverse compounds. In order to maintain the balance of the activity of the free radicals in living cells, the organism has evolved antioxidant defense systems, protecting against free radical damage. However, when our endogenous defense system has incomplete efficiency, or a rise in free radicals under special conditions like smoking, chemical air pollutants, radiation, and inflammation, the imbalance between free radicals and antioxidants results in oxidative stress, which is now believed to be one of the important factors in the occurrence of certain human diseases including atherosclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis, cancer, and neurodegenerative diseases. So, the search of possible antioxidants agents is of interest, because they protect the body against damage by harmful free radicals. For this purpose two copper(II) coordination compounds of 1-(morpholin-4-yl) propane-1,2-dione 4-allylthiosemicarbazone (HL) with 1,10-phenantroline (1,10-Phen) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (2,2'-Bpy) were synthesized. On the first stage of the experiment the ethanolic solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reacts with 4-allylthiosemicarbazone HL and on the second stage the ethanolic solution of the prepared precursor $\text{Cu}(\text{L})\text{NO}_3$ reacts with bidentate amines forming crystalline coordination compounds. The composition of these compounds was determined using elemental analysis for copper: $\text{Cu}(1,10\text{-Phen})(\text{L})\text{NO}_3$, $\text{Cu}(2,2'\text{-Bpy})(\text{L})\text{NO}_3$. The molar conductivity values of the synthesized coordination compounds are in the range $82\text{-}98 \Omega^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ that indicates that these complexes are 1:1 electrolytes. A standard ABTS⁺ method has been used to determine the antioxidant properties of synthesized compounds and trolox was used as a reference. The pro-ligand HL is less active than trolox, its coordination to copper(II) atom decreases antioxidant activity. The introduction of bidentate amines into the internal sphere of precursor increases the activity of complexes, that become 4 times more active than pro-ligand HL, 6 times more active than precursor, and also more active than trolox.

Table 1. IC_{50} values of the synthesized substances toward ABTS⁺ radical cation.

Compound	IC_{50} , μM
HL	94.44
$\text{Cu}(\text{L})\text{NO}_3$	140.30
$\text{Cu}(1,10\text{-Phen})(\text{L})\text{NO}_3$	23.04
$\text{Cu}(2,2'\text{-Bpy})(\text{L})\text{NO}_3$	22.31
Trolox	33.00

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Key words: antioxidants agents, Copper(II) coordination compounds, harmful free radicals.

**SYNTHESIS OF NEW *EPI*-MANOYLOXIDE DERIVATIVES WITH AZIDE
AND *gamma*-LACTAM FUNCTIONAL GROUPS**

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Manoyloxides have the carbon skeleton of the natural diterpenoid forskolin, which is a relevant secondary metabolite isolated from *Coleus forskohlii* with a myriad of therapeutic activities based on its ability to penetrate the cell membranes and stimulate the enzyme adenylyl cyclase. Other natural products belonging to the *ent*-series like ribenol and varodiol share the same tricyclic structure of manoyloxides and both have been reported in structure-activity relationship studies, providing derivatives with antimicrobial properties. These facts prompts following synthetic studies aimed to the generation of other manoyloxides derivatives with more and diverse functional groups.

We report in the current communication the free radical carboazidation of epimeric manoyloxide leading to azide-functionalized epimanoyloxide and converted successfully to a related *gamma*-lactame. The lactamization step occurred spontaneously on catalytic hydrogenation of carboazidation product. The structure of the title product was demonstrated by spectroscopic means and showed a flexible nitrogen-centered chirality, which is characteristic for such hybrid heterocycles.

The *gamma*-lactame is regarded as a surrogate of GABA derivatives and proved to be an efficient pharmacophore in our recent studies. Following investigations are in progress in order to reveal the cytotoxicity mechanism displayed by similar terpenic *gamma*-lactams.

Key words: antimicrobial properties, *gamma*-lactame *Coleus forskohlii*, manoyloxides, spectroscopic methods,

PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF SOME MOLDOVAN WHITE AND RED GRAPE VARIETIES AT DIFFERENT MATURATION PERIODS

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Viticulture, along with the winemaking, is the main food industry of Republic of Moldova, whose development is in a close relation with the country's economy [1]. Annually, hundreds of thousands of tons of grapes [2] are used to produce wines, juices, jams etc. – a job in which 25% of the working population of the country is involved [1].

Grapes are rich sources of different classes of polyphenols that possess antioxidant activity and are benefic for the humans' health. At different maturation periods, the content of the polyphenols in grapes varies within the grapes' tissues due to the biochemical processes that occur during the development of the berries [3].

In this study, the polyphenolic content and the antioxidant activity was determined in two white grape varieties of new selection, Viorica and Riton, and two red grape varieties, Feteasca Neagra and Copceac. All tests were accomplished at three different maturation periods: in unripe grapes, at the veraison and at the ripening. Various eco-friendly extraction methods were used in order to ensure the extraction of the grapes' polyphenols and antioxidants from the constituent parts of the berries: squeezing, ethanol – HCl extraction or thermal extraction. Spectral and analytical methods were applied for the qualitative determination of the particular groups of phenolic compounds. Thereby, the anthocyanins were analyzed by the pH differential method [4], the presence of the proanthocyanidins was established by using the DMACA reagent [5] and total phenolic content was determined through the Folin – Ciocalteu method [6]. The antioxidant assay was performed by utilizing the DPPH free radical [7], thanks to the accessibility and reproducibility of the method. A good correlation between the polyphenolic content and antioxidant activity of the grape extracts was established.

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Key words: antioxidant activity, phenolic compounds, grape varieties, grape extracts, maturation periods.

COPPER COMPOUNDS AS STRESS FACTORS AND REGULATORS
IN PHYCOBIOTECHNOLOGY

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Metals are part of the structural component of the active centers of key enzymes involved in the reactions on which life is based. In the course of evolution, living organisms have developed mechanisms that allow them to acquire metals from the environment. The vast majority of metals with a known biological value belong to the category of microelements. The existence of natural habitats with a high content of metals, and recently anthropogenic pollution of the environment with metals, have led to the emergence of mechanisms for protecting cells from the harmful effects of increased amounts of these chemical elements.

Microalgae and cyanobacteria, especially freshwater ones, in their natural environment are deficient in essential metals and have effective mechanisms for their capture and active transport into cells. Under technological conditions, the replenishment of the nutrient medium with metals in various forms is an effective method for controlling cellular biosynthetic processes. At the same time, metals, especially those with variable valence, are a source of free radicals that can threaten both the biotechnological process and the quality of biomass. The effect depends not only on the amount of metal, but also on the chemical form in which it is present.

In the case of biotechnologies involving the cyanobacterium *Arthrospira platensis* (spirulina), this can be demonstrated using copper as an example. Copper is an important component of more than metalloenzymes, including superoxide dismutase and cytochrome c oxidase. At the same time, being in the ionic form, even at a concentration of 2.5 mg/l, copper disrupts the growth of the culture, and at a concentration of 0.1 mg/l causes serious changes, expressed in the deterioration of the biomass quality, a decrease in the activity of antioxidant enzymes, and accumulation of products of oxidative degradation of biopolymers.

As a structural part of the coordinating compounds, copper is tolerated by the spirulina culture in much greater amounts, even providing a stimulatory effect, the extent of which is determined by both the amount of metal and the nature of the coordinating agent used in the synthesis of compounds. Thus, using copper in the composition of the compound in an amount of from 1 to 20 mg/l, it is possible to obtain a spirulina biomass with a modified content of pigments, lipids, carbohydrates and proteins.

Copper nanoparticles also have a high biological activity against spirulina, which is determined by a number of factors, such as the size of the nanoparticles, the method of their synthesis, and their quantity. The biological activity of copper nanoparticles becomes noticeable already at a concentration of 1 µg/L. Thus, depending on the form and applied concentration, copper can be both a major stressor and an effective biotechnological regulator.

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Key words: *Arthrospira platensis*, biotechnology, enzymes, nanoparticles.

IMPROVING SUNFLOWER CROP BIODIVERSITY, BY CREATING NEW, MORE PERFORMANT GENOTYPES

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Biodiversity is the diversity of life on earth, including plants, animals, fungi, and microorganisms. At the genetic level, biodiversity includes the diversity found between varieties and landraces of the same crop, but also extends to diversity present in crop wild relatives.

There are efforts of scientists exploring agrobiodiversity, to develop genetic tools critical for improving crop performance to support both resilience to climate stresses, and local adaptation to low-input agriculture. Oilseed sunflower accounts for up to 12% of the worldwide production of vegetable oils, ranking fourth after palm, soybean and canola oil. Compared to the other main temperate crops, cultivated sunflower is a recent crop. It experienced a domestication bottleneck that narrowed its genetic base but the large number of sunflower CWR makes it possible to mine a vast genetic pool for crop improvement. The use of CWR in the sunflower breeding is a long tradition in the breeding programs. A significant number of inbred lines have been created by interspecific crosses. These lines, together with the wild populations, represent a valuable resource of useful alleles that are abundantly used in the breeding program for increasing genetic variability. There have been introduced resistance genes to economically significant pathogens and parasitic plants, increasing tolerance to herbicides and altering the architecture of the plant.

Current research on CWR is focused on the discovery of new resistance genes to the more virulent populations of *Orobanche cumana*.

By using a very various and valuable germplasm, in different breeding programs there have been obtained valuable inbred lines, having very good characteristics.

It has been obtained an important genetic progress, regarding the productivity, also different agronomic and physiological traits and adaptation to the biotic and abiotic factors.

There have been studied some new sunflower hybrids – contribution of genetic diversity to increasing of productivity.

Key words: biodiversity, sunflower, interspecific crosses, genetic variability, genetic progress.